

THE LUNAR CRATERING CHRONOLOGY: EXPLORATION-ENABLED SCIENCE SUCCESS. C.

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Background: The lunar cratering chronology is a tool for determining absolute model ages (AMAs) for unsampled geological units across the Moon via crater size-frequency distribution (CSFD) measurements [e.g., 1-8], and it can be modified to use on other planetary bodies [e.g. 3,4,9,10]. A chronology function (CF) is fit to a dataset containing (1) the radio-isotopic or exposure dates for lunar samples of known provenance, and (2) the cumulative number of craters \geq a reference diameter, typically 1 km, for the unit interpreted to represent the sample (Fig. 1). The $N(1)$ values that feed into the historical calibration were produced with Apollo and Lunar Orbiter data and samples ages. Technical advancements in instrumentation as well as new image data from recent lunar missions, allow the calibration points to be tested and updated [e.g., 11-15].

With these datasets, the CF relies on samples of Imbrium basin ejecta (Descartes and Fra Mauro Formations, radioisotopic ages of ~ 3.9 Ga), mare basalts (radioisotopic ages of ~ 3.2 - 3.7 Ga), ropey glasses from the Apollo 12 landing site interpreted as Copernicus ejecta (radioisotopic age of ~ 850 Ma), and cosmic-ray exposure ages of ejecta and secondary crater materials of the Tycho, North Ray, and Cone craters [e.g. 16,17 and references therein]. However, the absence of samples with ages between 3.2 Ga and 850 Ma caused a large gap in the calibration

Figure 1. The lunar cratering chronology curve (black) of Neukum (1983)[2], which is fit to radio-isotopic and exposure ages of Apollo and Luna samples and $N(1)$ values determined for the sample units. Our ongoing work is updating the historical points, and producing internally consistent new reference points. Calibrations for SPA or other ancient basins are not straightforward.

tion dataset that created ambiguity in the best approach for fitting CFs [e.g. 17].

Filling the Gap: Sample-return mission concepts and proposals thus focused on returning samples that represent either the oldest of the lunar basins (South Pole-Aitken basin, [e.g., 18,19]) or some of the youngest lunar mare basalts (P60 basalt south of Aristarchus crater [e.g., 20-24]; Mons Rümker or Em4/P58 basalt [25]). Indeed, the Chinese exploration program selected sample-return sites that have helped fill the gap!

The Chang'e-5 (CE5) mission returned samples of ca. 2 Ga old mare basalts from Em4/P58 at the end of 2020, and the Change'e-6 (CE6) mission brought back samples from ca. 2.8 Ga old mare deposits in the southern part of the Apollo basin on the farside in 2024. The radio-isotopic dates for the CE5 [26,27] and CE6 [28,29] samples allow the addition of new calibration points to the lunar cratering chronology. In particular, calibration points can be added for the young basalt units [e.g. 29-32]. Some returned material is also thought to represent the SPA basin [29].

Summary: An improved calibration of the lunar chronology allows a clearer and more granular interpretation of the geological history of the Moon and other bodies where the lunar chronology is applied. Samples returned as part of exploration programs are fantastic examples of ground-breaking exploration-enabled science.

References: [1] Hartmann et al. (1981) BVTP 1049-1128; [2] Neukum (1983) Habil Thesis; [3] Neukum and Ivanov (1994) in Hazards Due to Comets and Asteroids, 359-416; [4] Neukum et al. (2001) Space Sci Rev 96, 55-86; [5] Stöffler and Ryder (2001) Space Sci Rev 96, 9-54; [6] Stöffler et al. (2006) Rev Min Geochem 60, 519-596; [7] Le Feuvre and Wicczorek (2011) Icarus 214, 1-20; [8] Robbins (2014) JGR Planets 124, 871-892; [9] Hartmann and Neukum (2001) Space Sci Rev 96, 165-194; [10] Hiesinger et al. (2016) Science 353, 6303; [11] Hiesinger et al. (2012) JGR 117, 2011JE003935; [12] Iqbal et al. (2019) Icarus 333, 528-547; [13] Iqbal et al. (2020) Icarus 352, 113991; [14] Iqbal et al. (2023) Icarus 406, 115732; [15] Iqbal et al. (2026) Icarus 444, 116791; [16] Cohen et al. (2023) Rev Min Geochem, 89, 10.2138/rmg.2023.89.09; [17] Hiesinger et al. (2023) Rev Min Geochem, 89, 10.2138/rmg.2023.89.10; [18] Jolliff et al. (2012) LEAG, 3047; [19] Jolliff et al. (2017) LPSC 48, 1326; [20] Hiesinger et al. (2003) JGR 108, 10.1029/2002JE001985; [21] Eldridge et al. (2010) LPSC 41, 1486; [22] Lawrence et al. (2013) LEAG, 7048; [23] Draper et al. (2019) LPSC 50, 1110; [24] Anderson et al. (2015) Issues in Crater Studies, 9058; [25] Qian et al. (2018) JGR 123, 2018JE005595; [26] Che et al. (2021) Science 374, 887-890; [27] Li Q. et al., (2021) Nat Sci Rev, nwab188; [28] Cui et al. (2025) Science 386, 1395-1399; [29] Su et al. (2025) National Science Review 12, nwaf103; [30] Yue et al. (2022) Nature Astronomy 6, 541-545; [31] van der Bogert et al. (2022) LPSC 53, 2440; [32] van der Bogert et al. (2026) LPSC, 1649.